

Appendix-01 FOR

Greenhouse gas emissions of India's household food, apparel, mobility and energy consumption: Regional structure and inequality, and scenarios for 1.5°C climate stabilization

Shelly Bogra^{1,2*}, Felix Creutzig^{3,4}, Peter-Paul Pichler⁵

¹ Norwegian Institute for Air Research

²The IDP in Climate Studies, IIT Bombay, India

³ Mercator Institute for the Global Commons (MCC), Berlin, Germany

⁴ Technical University Berlin, Berlin, Germany

⁵ Social Metabolism and Impacts, Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research, Member of the Leibniz Association, PO Box 60 12 03, D-14412, Potsdam, Germany

* Corresponding author, e-mail: sbog@nilu.no, shbogr@gmail.com

This document provides supplementary information on methods, data and figures for the results indicated in the main paper. The document starts with notes providing additional information on various methodologies used in this assessment.

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S.1 Data and methodology for scenarios assessment

S.1.1 Data and limitations

The complete list of commodities analyzed in this assessment is reported in Table T.1, whereas Table T.2 offers emission-intensities of respective products. It is assumed that commodities included in Table T.1 serve as an indicator for current (2018-2019) and future patterns of consumption. Table T.2 indicates the sources from where the value of emissions data are retrieved.

S.1.1.1 Consumption data

The National Sample Survey (NSS) Organisation reports offer consumption data across rural and urban demography for the period 2011-2012 [3]. The data is available for twelve expenditure categories in terms of monthly per capita expenditure (MPCE) in monetary or physical units with different time-per, namely, uniform reference period (URP) (a fixed 7 days period, usually for edibles), mixed reference period (MRP) (7 and 30 days, incorporating edibles, transportation, fuel, and electricity, and clothing among others), and modified mixed reference period (MMRP) (7, 30, and 365 days, incorporating capital goods, bedding etc.). This assessment used data referring to MRP time-period since all considered commodities (Table T.1) were adequately represented in this period.

Table T.1: Consumption data in MRP category

Commodities available	
physical units (Kg)	price units *(Rupees)
rice	milk & milk products
wheat	sugar
jowar	salt
bajra	edible oil
maize	egg, fish & meat
barley	vegetables
small millets	fruits (fresh)
ragi	fruits (dry)
gram	spices
cereal subst.	beverages etc.
arahar	fuel and light
gram (split)	clothing
moong	footwear
masur	conveyance/ transportation
urd	
peas	
khesari	
other pulses	
pulse products	

The referred databases [3, 4], report consumption data in both physical and monetary units. However, for the estimation of emissions, data of consumption is required in physical units only. Thus, when data was reported in monetary units only[3], the first step was to convert the data into physical units, for the appropriate determination of commodity-specific emissions. The conversion is mathematically presented in Equation 1, wherein,

$$q_{s,p,i,c} = \frac{pr_{s,p,i,c}}{up_{s,c}} \quad (1)$$

$q_{s,p,i,c}$ represents quantity, q of a commodity, c consumed by per capita in an expenditure category, i , in region, p (rural or urban) of the state, s . The right hand side (RHS) term in the numerator of the Equation 1, $pr_{s,p,i,c}$ refers to price spent by an income category, i , on the commodity, c , in the geography, p (rural or

urban), of the state s , whereas the latter $up_{s,c}$ indicates the average unit price of the commodity c in the state s and was retrieved from [4].

Since the objective of this study does not include highlighting the key differences in data collection arising on account of three different time-periods, variability in the estimation of emissions due to numbers reported for the three categories (URP, MRP, and MMRP), is excluded from this assessment. Additionally, in this study, results reported at the national level are obtained by averaging state-level results and are not based on an all-India average, as stated in the referred documents [4, 3].

That said, for determination of total emissions (TE) and carbon-inequality at the national level, the expenditure-classes for rural and urban areas were re-organized as per the level of consumption expenditure, and the population was distributed equally across 10 different quantiles. That is, first and second quantiles were combined as lowest 10% and, eleventh and twelfth ECs were grouped into the last quantile of 90 to 100%.

Commodities excluded from current assessment Referring to NSS’s consumer-expenditure database, this study excludes construction goods (buildings, roads, airports, hospitals, etc.) as rental payments are not incorporated in current assessment (see NSS [3] Table 6B U/R all India). That is, the role of the construction sector in the consumer-expenditure account is not assessed. Reason being, such goods are long term stocks, bought for decades by households, the rental payments have to be estimated for years if not decades to calculate an accurate estimate of consumption. The contribution of other consumer goods (cars, scooters, TVs, refrigerators, etc.) is also excluded for the same reasoning.

Note on emissions of high expenditure-categories For luxury, premium products used by higher expenditure-strata, it is to be noted that the high ECs and government operations would have a larger contribution. However, since such information is excluded from the consumer survey, it is difficult to assess their impacts. That is, for high ECs and government-officials, transportation emissions are expected to be higher due to their owning private luxurious aeroplanes and yachts, high-end security vehicles, among others. Additionally, these high ECs would be buying clothes and footwear from fashion centres of the world. Hence, it is expected that emissions from such consumption would be missing from domestic-consumption accounts. This may be a case of carbon-leakage from consumption-perspective and can be explored in future studies.

Scope of NSS survey It is to be noted that the household survey accounts for 1109 million people for 2012, whereas the World Bank reported population was approximately 1250 million [5]. Hence, nearly 140 million people were unaccounted in this survey. It is expected that these missing numbers belong to the categories excluded in the survey (page 16- section 1.6.2 [3]). For detailed understanding and limitations of statistical data, refer to methodological choices indicated in consumer survey [4, 3, 6].

S.1.1.2 Emissions data

The Table T.2 report emission intensities (carbon-emission equivalents, CO₂eq or emission intensity) retrieved from the literature. As indicated in the Methodology section of the main paper, Table T.2 captures Scope 1 emissions [7] of transportation and fuel-use (direct, owned by consumers [8], and dependent on the intensity of use). Scope 2 emissions are for domestic electricity-use, i.e., GHG emissions from the generation of purchased electricity consumed, occurring at the facility where electricity is generated [8]. And Scope 3 emissions for products belonging to food, clothing, and footwear categories (occurring from sources not owned or controlled by the user [8]). Thus, food-based emissions include those occurring on farm-site, clothing-emissions refer to textile-industries, and footwear includes rubber-based emissions, with sources of data indicated in Table T.2.

Since regional emissions inventories of products/commodities are unavailable in India, this study used equal emission intensities of products and services across all regions (as indicated in Table T.2), thus excluding impacts from the supply-chains. That is, national emission intensities (equal across states) of electricity, fuel and transportation used in this assessment [9] exclude regional impacts. Thereby, the critical limitation of this assessment is the lack of variability arising on account of regional product emission factors and supply-chains integral to this assessment. Above limitation implies that indirect cost of materials, losses, among others, are also excluded from these estimates of commodity-wise emissions.

Table T.2: Commodity-wise emission factors

Commodity	kg CO ₂ eq. per kg (Range)	Source and notes
rice	1.752	[6]
wheat	0.29	[6]
jowar	0.347	[6]
bajra	0.156	[6]
maize	0.21	[6]
barley	0.048	[6]
small millets	0.156	[6]
ragi	0.156	[6]
gram	0.282	[6]
cereal subst.	0.221	[6]
arahar	0.601	[6]
gram (split)	0.282	[6]
moong	0.541	[6]
masur	0.541	[6]
urd	0.541	[6]
peas	0.362	[6]
khesari	0.541	[6] ¹
other pulses	0.362	[6]
pulse products	0.362	[6]
milk and milk products ²	8.775 (4.5 - 90)	[6] milk - 95% others - 5%
sugar	0.148	[6]
sugar	0.194	[6]
edible oil	2.402	[6]
egg, fish & meat ²	16.608 (1.507-75.556)	[6]
vegetables ²	0.044	[6]
fruits (fresh) ²	0.043	[6]
fruits (dry) ²	0.210	[6]
spices ²	0.000	[6] - consumption in grams
beverages etc. ²	0.004	[6] - wine, beer, toddy etc.
fuel and light ²	2.303 (1.22-3.13)	[9] dung cake to L.P.G.
clothing	0.843	[10] - cotton yarn
footwear	30.506	estimated from [11, 12] - rubber emissions
	3256.266	2009 -data [11], KtCO ₂ eq
	106.743	2009 -data [12], Kt
conveyance/transport ²	2.480 (2.3-2.66)	[9] - petrol and diesel

¹ Same as moong² Multiple commodities are combined

To circumvent this issue, the use of regional input-output models is well advocated in the industrial-ecology literature. However, such models, focusing on emissions in the current study, are not available for India for the considered period. A national-level input-output model for CO₂-emissions was developed for 2003-04 [13]; however, use of this model's estimates would not circumvent the issue of regional intensities of emissions. Such calculations could cause serious double-counting issues, owing to the overlapping of supply-chain boundaries. Additionally, the estimates would also be needed to be revised for the later period of 2011-12, for which consumer expenditure survey is available from NSS reports. Thus, discarding this model, we used the estimates that are currently being used for recent energy and food, assessments [9, 6]. Since the development of regional input-output models is beyond the scope of this study, it is highly recommended for future studies.

Additionally, it is stressed that using data from IO models apt procedure be followed for providing concordance between IO sector's data and consumer expenditure's product-level data. That is, without apt conversions, sector-wise intensities from CO₂-based IO regional models should be appropriately allocated to commodities. It is to be noted that it is not easy to estimate the GHG contribution of milk or meat emissions from a consumption-perspective using IO-based models without concrete data and methodology such as life-cycle assessment. Thus, the use of other datasets such as those from FAO are usually used as a proxy. For example, Rao et al. [6] used FAO statistics. These differences are important for life-cycle assessments studies as well. The aggregated nature of IO-table (employed by [13]) also fails to highlight the difference between rice versus other grains.

S.1.1.3 Population data

The population data of the MRP category is retrieved from the NSS report [3]. The report provides an estimate of the population for each expenditure-category (EC) for both rural and urban areas. The dataset is therefore used for estimation of total emissions by an (EC). That is, total emissions of each (EC) are estimated by multiplying per capita emissions of each category with the total population of each (EC).

S.1.2 Note on transportation emissions

For transportation (given as conveyance category in consumer surveys)- based emissions, construction-based (production-based emissions driving large-scale infrastructures, such as metro-systems, or road, railways, etc.) emissions are excluded from the calculation of transportation-based emissions. However, fuel-use (gasoline) are included for estimation (with apt conversions and aggregation) as transportation-based expenditure is reported in the consumer survey. For rural-India, it is to be noted that for local travel, service provided by draught animals such as bullock or horse-carts is excluded from the calculations. It is reiterated that travel emissions are estimated after conversion from monetary to physical units, as indicated in Table T.1.

S.1.3 Note on the term 'footprint'

The term 'footprint' includes only emissions (CO₂ and CO₂-equivalents for agri-derived commodities) from a consumption-perspective; and, excludes emissions associated with sequestration (due to natural and engineered technologies [14]) and upstream supply-chains. The latter estimation would require supply-chains evaluation at rural and urban boundaries, through the use of approaches such as LCA or physical accounting-based multi-regional emissions-oriented input-output models, etc., among others. Such methodological assessments and models are currently non-existent for India.

S.1.4 Note on the power sector emissions

From a consumption perspective, direct use of the output from the power-sector, i.e., electricity by the final consumers in a specific region (or state) depends on both the technology used for power-generation capacity as well as inter-state buying and selling system of electricity-sector.

Considering the power-distribution structure of electricity across India, it is easily seen that nearly all states of India have coal power generation ([15]), with nuclear and renewable also disbursed across the nation

(operating within coal-based regions as well), it can be safely assumed due to grid connectivity that carbon-emissions of India (primarily due to coal-use) are fairly constant across the nation. For example, states with a higher share of hydro such as northern states of Uttarakhand (pg 5 –[16], [17]) and northeastern states such as Nagaland ([18]), Manipur ([19]) buy a significant portion of – thermal power from other states although their direct CO₂ emissions, as accounted in the current system of emissions-accounting, are negligible. Thus, even though hydro or other sources (solar, wind, nuclear, biofuel, etc.) are part of the regional structure, such green-infrastructures are supported by thermal power-plants at various levels owing to variability in the performance of the main inputs, changing water-levels, wind-level, day-time operations of solar-panels, among etc.

For example, considering the from a technological perspective, for biomass-based power generation, apart from technology used, environmental factors (soil type, soil water chemistry and fertilization also affect feedstock-inherent ash concentration and its elemental ash composition [20]) would be a decisive factor for inter-seasonal variation of emission-generation.

Considering the operational requirements of thermal power plants, only a few states have coal mines that can support the requirements of power plants in other states. The emission-factor of gasoline (predominantly used in transportation and industrial operations) is nearly constant since it is processed from crude and natural gas is simply transported. Considering coal-supply structure, coal processing may happen in another state /region than where the actual coal power plant is located. For example, it is very likely that coal used in state's (Z= Gujarat) power plant is procured in the processed form from a region outside the state's own boundary (can be mined in state X -an international location such Carmichael mine in Australia or the state of Jharkhand; processed in state Y=Chattisgarh and, used in State Z). Since coal mines are confined to certain regions and usually support many power plants, the embodied emissions from input-characteristics (it is expected that quality of coal from a mine also remains the same) would remain same wherever the input is used. That is, if the same mine is supporting coal for various destinations across the nation, with processing-methods, or plant-loading factors remaining the same, the emissions are not likely to vary much across the inter-regional production structure as well. Thus, the emissions from the production of coal-based power, are expected to be fairly constant over regions. Further, as stated above, emissions would get embodied in regions due to the inter-connectivity of the grid.

Further, we need to consider that a substantial part of electricity- produced is consumed in the industrial sector, which again is part of inter-regional supply-chains that may support non-local consumers through storage and transportation systems. For example, the electricity-dependent irrigation systems of Punjab for Paddy production support the demand of Basmati consumers from national and international urban centres. Or, consider the role of embodied electricity in industrial processes (from irrigation to fertilization) in dairy products supply or vegetables or fruit supply. The fruits grown in north-India end up as jams and sauces in various parts of India. The role of power-sector from the final harvest of products (rice, vegetables, fruits, milk) to packaging, distribution, storage, till the final consumer would be consisting of major inter-regional power consumption. Thus, from a consumption perspective, when local is not consumed locally, the 'local' regional-structure loses its significance.

As it is only fossil (coal, gas, etc.) sources whose CO₂ emissions would be accounted at the state or national level, variability in the emissions may not be much either. Therefore, considering various aspects of power-structure from a consumption perspective, assuming a national emission-factor from consumption-perspective is not an illogical one. Thereby, households CO₂ emissions can be safely assumed to be fairly constant in interconnected regions.

Therefore, the inter-regional aspect of any resource-use may seem a lucrative proposition to investigate; however it would not yield many benefits if endless inputs and outputs are disbursed all over the space. In such a context, using aggregated spatial information is a better proposition to achieve the goals of the consumption-based or household-based research question. Therefore, the same is attempted in this assessment. In the context of policy-decisions on low-carbon infrastructure implementation, territorial emissions may not be associated with local consumption.

Last, for emissions of products imported from other countries, their national (since it is expected that their regional supply-chains are also distributed within the whole country) emissions should be employed. Since the consumer-survey of 2011-12 do not offer any indicator of imported goods and services, such an assessment is out of the scope of this study. Therefore such implications were not suggested either.

That said, from both production and consumption perspectives, if all the trade of inputs and outputs

is constrained to a single region, or at least input-resource is an entirely local resource (water, pollination, biodiversity- local ecosystem services). Only then it would make sense to derive regional emission-intensities.

S.1.5 Note on the development and use of regional IO models

Regional EEIO models should be developed for local resources such as water, biodiversity, etc. for better estimation of impacts for sustainable use of resources. However, the development of regional IO databases can not address the issue related to inter-state supply-chain emissions, since we are interested in inter-regional supply-chains.. Therefore, only multi-regional EEIO-model will be able to circumvent the problem at hand, i.e., consumption-impacts of inter-state supply-chains (see the above response to power-sector emissions from consumption perspective).

Even for the regional EEIO models, IO-accounts need to be converted to environmental accounts, for which inventories of environmental-goods needs to be constructed. Development of such inventories (see Bogra et al., 2016 [21]) is not a trivial task either, for 130 sectors (2003-04 IOTT of India), at the regional level. Consider this, each state has to provide all energy-use and emissions data for 100 plus sectors. Furthermore, from the consumption-perspective of one India economy, since an emissions-oriented multi-regional input-output (MRIO) model would be required, it would involve using inter-regional supply-chains data for outlining inter-sectoral trade flows, ideally in physical units. That is, apart from each state's own inter-sectoral data, data would be required for each state's imports and exports, for other 30 plus states of India and one for the world (or multi-country economy if possible) economy.

Additionally, if build, such an MRIO would need to adhere to apt allocations and concordance with national IO model based on physical-units for multi-sectors observed within the economy since such measures are necessary for material and energy balancing sought by EEIO models. Thus, EEIO models built and used under life cycle assessment framework are preferred by the Industrial Ecology community. However, the building of such an MRIO-model at the national scale (covering all the states, or, if aggregated for regions-north, west, east, south) is not a trivial task when inter-regional data is non-existent in the required format.

Further, the level of adequate tools (software, algorithm, computational power) and frameworks to capture information on inter-regional trade and afterwards make reasonable assumptions on allocations of material and energy used are also rigorously pursued by EEIO-oriented research teams. However, even though numerous assessments have been attempted, the research-teams do acknowledge certain limitations of the studies. The major caveat stated in such studies is massive aggregation issues and disconnect in the time-based sector-wise production (extrapolated to support same base-year calculations). Further, another issue that affects nearly all regional IO studies is the homogeneity of prices for sectors and mass/energy balancing. The implications of all these assumptions and limitations of assessment based on the same models are well-documented in the EEIO literature. In short, building and using such a database at a global level without aggregation is a significant effort indeed (see Industrial Ecology Lab, University of Sydney, EXIOBASE, EORA, WIOD).

Summarizing, the development of multi-regional physical IO models using physical accounting for emissions accounting would definitely assist in assessing environmental impacts attributed to consumption. However, such models are not easy to build owing to lack of data for inter-regional data on supply-chains and environmental resource inventories in the regional context.

S.1.6 Defining National Expenditure Deciles

The NSS [4] combines the expenditure-stratified populations of the states in a relative manner to obtain national deciles. In this case, for example, the first national decile includes the 10% of the lowest spending people of each state. Since the absolute spending levels of the different states differ widely and carbon emissions depend on the absolute level of consumption, we have decided to recalculate the national deciles. To do this, we approximate the national expenditure distribution by allocating to the partial population in each state-level decile their average per capita expenditure and calculate new deciles on this basis. This means that the first decile now includes the lowest spending 10% of the national Indian population. We believe that this representation is better suited to reflect the carbon impact of different consumption classes.

S.2 Methodology: Scenarios

The state-level population forecast till 2050 is unavailable for India. Therefore, first, total national population projections were estimated aligning with the numbers of [22]. The estimates of national population (2012-2050) were allocated at state-level for all ECs (Section S.2.1) assuming that current CoVID-pandemic will not wipe out millions during 2020-21 itself [23, 24]. The respective populations of different states were multiplied with per capita (household) emissions (Section S.2.2) of states from 2012 to 2050 to generate state-wise emissions. These state-level emissions were summed to obtain national-level emissions, represented as BAU emissions. Further, the socio-technical transformations [25] (Section S.2.3) are evaluated from 2021-22 onwards considering the impact of current pandemic. Additionally, all scenarios are subject to certain conditions such as the range of thresholds used in this assessment would also change due to uncertainty [26] in global estimates, such as those about the global budget of food-based emissions 4.3-5.7 GtCO₂eq [27], higher emissions under 2°C, discounting period, and population estimates at state-level.

S.2.1 Population projection

For India, national and regional-level population forecast is unavailable till 2050. Therefore, first, the population was projected at the national level. Thereafter, projections were made at state-level for all ECs. The projections forecast account for the reduction in the growth of population along with rural to urban migration, among others, as described next.

Using UN’s Indian population data for 2020, national population projections ($Total_population_{20XX}$) were made from 2021 to 2050 following the numbers projected by a recent study [22]. In the mentioned study, the yearly numbers till 2100 are not available in the supporting information of [22] -else we would have used them), while the estimates ($Total_population_{20XX}$ from 2010 to 2019 were used for validating the numbers for the same period.

The national projection for 2022-2050 is based on the assumption that annual increase in population declines at the rate of 0.005% of 1% of previous year’s population while the backcasting assumes a rise of 0.01% of 1% of current year’s population from 2019 to 2010. The assumed rates are based on growth reported in UN projections [28], with backcast numbers following closely with [28]. In our estimates from 2021 to 2050, peak occurs in 2051 (with 1614 million), while for 2048 (peak in [22] at 1606 million) the number is 1610 million. Thus, our forecast differs from [22] by 0.2%.

It is to be noted that we have made a simple percentage-based forecast from 2021 following yearly growth rate recorded in [28]; whereas, the estimates of [22] are based on multiple variables (age, sex, fertility, etc.). From 2050 onwards, the average growth rate is nearly zero as per our function, which in turn stabilizes population at 1609 million in 2070. The limitation of this approach is that only a single population-projection is evaluated at the national level, as population forecast using parameters considered in [22] are beyond the scope of this assessment. The population numbers are indicated in Columns 3,7 of Table T.3; whereas, the detailed calculation is given in Appendix-03, Tab: “Total Population projection”.

The nation-wide projected numbers of the total population are decreased further (Columns 4,8 of Table T.3) to align with the expected coverage of NSS [3](total population of India was 1250 million in 2011 while only 1109 million were captured in NSS; thus only 0.89% of the population was accounted). These numbers (from 2012 to 2050) were further allocated to states, in proportion to ratio indicated in 2011-12 NSS population data. Additionally, distribution to different ECs was similar to the 2011-12 NSS data.

The rural and urban numbers were further revised to account for rural to urban migration from 2012 onwards. For the period 2012 to 2019, rural to urban migration rate is assumed to grow at 0.01% annually as a fraction of the rural population. This increases the fraction of the urban population from 29% in 2012 to 35% in 2020. In 2021 and 2022, the migration rate is assumed as zero owing to the current pandemic [23, 24]. Both urban and rural population of each expenditure-category (EC) for 2021 are increased (from the level of 2020) by the rates of population growth calculated using Equations 2 and 3,

$$Urban_Population_{2021,EC} = Urban_Population_{2020,EC} \frac{Total_population_{2021}}{Total_population_{2020}} \quad (2)$$

$$Rural_Population_{2021,EC} = Rural_Population_{2020,EC} \frac{Total_population_{2021}}{Total_population_{2020}} \quad (3)$$

Table T.3: Population in millions, Appendix-03, Tab “Total Population projection”

Year	UN stats [28]	Estimated	Revised	Year	UN stats	Estimated	Revised
2010	1234	1234		2041		1590	1412
2011		1249	1109	2042		1594	1415
2012		1265	1123	2043		1598	1419
2013		1279	1136	2044		1601	1422
2014		1294	1149	2045		1604	1424
2015	1310	1309	1162	2046		1606	1426
2016	1325	1323	1175	2047		1608	1428
2017	1339	1338	1188	2048		1610	1430
2018	1353	1352	1201	2049		1612	1431
2019	1366	1366	1213	2050		1613	1433
2020	1380	1380	1225	2051		1615	1434
2021		1394	1238	2052		1614	
2022		1408	1250	2053		1613	
2023		1421	1262	2054		1612	
2024		1435	1274	2055		1611	
2025		1448	1286	2056		1611	
2026		1460	1297	2057		1611	
2027		1473	1308	2058		1610	
2028		1485	1319	2059		1610	
2029		1496	1329	2060		1610	
2030		1507	1338	2061		1610	
2031		1518	1348	2062		1609	
2032		1528	1356	2063		1609	
2033		1537	1365	2064		1609	
2034		1546	1372	2065		1609	
2035		1554	1380	2066		1609	
2036		1561	1386	2067		1609	
2037		1568	1392	2068		1609	
2038		1574	1398	2069		1609	
2039		1580	1403	2070		1609	
2040		1585	1407	2071		1609	

wherein $Total_population_{2020}$ and $Total_population_{2020}$, represents the estimates $Total_Population_{20XX}$ indicated earlier. For 2023 to 2030, the rate of migration (it is assumed that recent pandemic will not alter the migration process permanently) is assumed to increase at a rate of 0.6% annually, following urban-share indicated in [28]. Thus, urban population for 2023 is estimated as 4 while rural is calculated by Equation 5.

$$Urban_Population_{2023,EC} = (Urban_Population_{2022,EC} + 0.006Rural_Population_{2022,EC}) \frac{Total_population_{2023}}{Total_population_{2022}} \quad (4)$$

$$Rural_Population_{2023,EC} = (Rural_Population_{2022,EC} - 0.006Rural_Population_{2022,EC}) \frac{Total_population_{2023}}{Total_population_{2022}} \quad (5)$$

Thus, migration allows for a decrease in the rural population while increasing urban numbers at the same time. Using the same source [28], migration rate is assumed as 0.65% for 2031 to 2040 and 0.7% per annum for 2041 to 2050. As indicated in the main manuscript, such a procedure allows the share of urban population to be 46% in 2050. The inter-state and international migrations are excluded from these state-wise estimates. See the details of these calculations in Appendix-03, Tab “RP_wM.D”.

Key limitation of this assessment: As indicated in the Section ‘Methodology’ of the main paper and outlined above, only a single projection of population is estimated at the national scale, based on a unique set of parameters. Thereby, the accurateness of projected population numbers may be taken with a pinch of salt as they represent only a single iteration among the infinite trajectories that are possible with the outlined procedure. Furthermore, the census data are available at decadal periods (2001, 2011, next at 2021). Further, owing to the current pandemic, transformations are started from 2021 onwards.

S.2.2 Emissions projections using per capita estimates

The World Bank (WB) [29] statistics indicate that Indian economy grew at an average rate of 6.74% (exponential estimated 5.054%) for 2012 to 2018 while total GHG emissions grew at 4.11% (exponential estimated 3.164%). The average contribution of households to GDP was 58% (2012 to 2018) [29], which is used for deriving total CO₂-based households emissions of India in our study. The data of agricultural emissions from the same source indicates that emissions grew at (exponential-growth) rate was 1.035% (see detailed calculations in Appendix-03, Tab: “WBdata.EG.Est.”). Using these values, it can be inferred that a 1% increase in GDP leads to an average increase of 0.626% (= 3.164/5.054) in total emissions and 0.20% in agricultural-based emissions. As total emissions grew at a higher rate than that of agricultural, non-crop based emissions are expected to grow at a higher rate. Assuming that emissions growth rate is equal for households and industries, non-agricultural emissions are estimated to increase at 0.88% for a percent increase in GDP.

Using the average national value ($\approx 62.6\%$) of emissions growth rate with the State GDPs from [30], emissions growth-rates of each state are evaluated from 2012 to 2018. These evaluated emissions growth-rates are further used for estimating per capita emissions of each EC from 2012 to 2018. As GDP Information is unavailable for 2019 [30], thus emissions growth-rate is assumed to be average of numbers evaluated for 2012 to 2018. Owing to the current CoVID pandemic zero growth rate was assumed for 2020 and 2021 or in other words, per capita emissions of 2020 and 2021 are considered equal to 2019. Literature indicates India’s economic growth rate will decline over the decades (page 10 [31]), thus implying emissions will decline accordingly. Therefore, to project per capita emissions from 2022 to 2050, it is assumed that average economic growth reduces 1.5% between each decade (state GDPs are reduced accordingly), leading to reduction of emissions growth-rate at 0.84% (this is the estimate by excluding UTs as no GDP is information for them) between the decades for the nation as a whole. Thus, average (national-level) emissions growth-rate of 3.23% for 2022 to 2030, 2.39% for 2031 to 2040, and 1.55% for 2041 to 2050 are obtained. It is assumed that the distribution of emissions across all ECs in any state remains the same throughout the period of evaluation (2012-2050), as are considered in recent studies [32, 33, 34]. The calculations of these estimations are indicated in Appendix-03, Tab: ‘Per-capita-projection-emissions growth -Statistics’. Thereby, the household

emissions are estimated by multiplying per capita emissions and population estimates (Section S.2.1) as mentioned above.

These household emissions are further allocated to specific categories in proportion to the ratio observed for 2011 NSS data (see Appendix-03, Tab: ‘Commodities-projected share- emissiongrowth-with migration’). The estimated numbers of fuel and electricity category are bifurcated between electricity (50% - pg of NSS [4] indicates equal expenditure on both) and domestic fuels. For industry, transportation and electricity emissions are expected to contribute 42% (58% is household’s contribution [29].) Thus, total emissions of the economy can be obtained by adding the estimates for households and industry. However, economy-wide total emissions are not used in this study since we focus only on the consumption-aspect.

S.2.3 Emissions scenarios: Households-based

As with the population-projections, estimated values of baseline emissions scenarios are evaluated separately for both rural and urban dimensions of each state. See Tab ‘TF_P_EGwM’ of the Appendix-03 (excel file) for details. However, they are represented in the results at the national level (by summing the state-wise rural and urban projections). The details of the baseline and other scenarios estimation are as follows.

Addressing the objective of Paris Climate Agreement and SDG 13, namely, reducing carbon emissions, in relation to other SDG goals, such as SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production) and SDG 10 (Reduced Inequality), scenarios described in the main manuscript offer an exploration of possible trajectories if various transformations suggested by “Club of Rome” [35] report are implemented to the Indian demography. Considering that emissions-results (Section 3.2 of the main paper), indicates that only four commodities (fuel including electricity, transportation, milk, and meat) contribute nearly 89% to total emissions, explored scenarios tackle these only. Further, as income plays a dominant role in consumption and total population correlates with spatial emissions, social transformations focus only on these two factors. It is to be noted that industrial-emissions for fuel & electricity and transportation category are excluded from current analysis even though industries contribute nearly 42% of total emissions [29] (while using nearly 55% energy-use since domestic energy demand 45% of total demand - pg 13 of [36]). Therefore, transformations are explored from consumption-perspective only in the main paper (summarized next).

The base-case Scenario, BAU, highlights the households’ emissions till 2050 if business as usual practices are followed and is evaluated by integrating average per capita emissions (Section S.2.2) and population projections (Section S.2.1) from 2011 to 2050.

Electricity-based emissions: The electricity-scenario, E_BAU, indicates households’ electricity-use emissions only and serves as the baseline for renewable energy (RE)-based transition. The RE-based scenario, E_S1, explores reduction due to growth in RE, estimated as E_R1 at the current rate. Thus, E_S1 highlights electricity-emissions with the assumption of 100% solar capacity (excludes hydro and the wind among others) at 3765 GW (2050) fulfilling all electricity requirements, with a generation of 1656 KWhr per annum for per unit (watt) installed. This capacity is a little higher than the suggested solar capacity of 3217 GW for 2050 (See Discussion [37]- PV single-axis and PV prosumers dominate the system with 2169 GW and 1048 GW, respectively), which excludes wind and hydro among others. Since only households consumption is considered in here, capacity is reduced to 2184 GW ($0.58 * 3765$) for E_S1. The RE installation is mapped according to logistic function (Equation 6, $C=2184$, $a= 153.58$) with growth rate ($0.172 = b1$) derived from observed statistics of solar from 2011 to 2017. Additionally, a higher growth rate ($0.23 = b2$) is also mapped since the observed one fails to achieve the target of 2184 GW by 2050. This rate of emissions reductions, E_R2, leads to Scenario, E_S2. See Figure F.10 for visualization and results in Table T.4. The complete calculations are given in Appendix-03, Tab:‘RE-emission-reduction’, with additional figure indicated in S.3.5.

$$y = C/(1 + a * exp(-bt)) \quad (6)$$

Comparison of our electricity-emission numbers with IESS’s projections: The IESS’s projects power-generation emissions (hydrocarbon based) of 5105 MtCO₂eq in 2047 under least effort scenario (similar to BAU) [38], which yields 5620 MtCO₂eq in 2050 under linear-extrapolation. Assuming 58% of electricity is used by households, this results in 3260 MtCO₂eq emissions in 2050 using IESS numbers, which is nearly equal to our projection of 3300 MtCO₂eq, differing by a margin of 1.2%. Under aggressive solar-capacity installation

with maximum potential 479 GW, IESS's projection for 2047 reduces power-generation emissions to 3258 MtCO₂eq, implying households' share of 1890 MtCO₂eq (58%). Thus, IESS's estimates for reduction are lower than our estimate under E_S2 owing different values of population and per unit generation. Additional reasons could be due to differences in assumptions about per unit power generation. IESS assumes power generation intensity of 4.18 KWhr compared to our estimate of 1.66 KWhr per Watt capacity installed (similar to [39] for 10 MW capacity), and 15% of maximum solar capacity suggested by [37]. Furthermore, IESS project their estimates with a higher population level, 1.7 billion in 2047, with equal economic growth under all scenarios, including for the electricity sector. In our study, the population is projected at a lower level (1.6 billion in 2050 - [22]) while emissions growth-rates for electricity and transportation are estimated at a higher rate than agricultural emissions.

Food-based emissions: The food-based emissions, represented as Scenario F_BAU, are estimated by integrating food-based per capita emissions with projected population from 2011 to 2050. Our numbers for 2011 align with the range indicated by [40], which estimates average per capita food-based emissions of India equal to 0.786 tCO₂eq, using data from 2011 to 2013. Additionally, since their study [40] estimated emissions adjusted for nutrition (baseline shift to 1.287 tCO₂eq per capita per year) and OECD-type of diets (2.899 tCO₂ per capita per year), we also estimate nutrition-based (at a lower rate of 1.287 tCO₂eq per capita) food-emissions transformation through scenario F_S1. However, we visualize this scenario from around 2028 onwards after meeting F_BAU in Figure 5(b) of the main manuscript.

Comparison of our food-emission numbers with IESS's projections: Comparison with IESS [38] reveals their agricultural-emissions estimates are based on tractor operations only.

Transportation-based emissions: The estimated results of transportation emissions (nearly 11% of households'emissions in 2011- Section 3.2 of the main paper) indicate a large share of highest 30% expenditure-households (nearly 69%) compared to lowest 30% (6% only). Thus, if the highest income-earners reduce their emissions, by reducing their unnecessary travel (material efficiency emissions reductions are excluded) within the avoid category [41], this could lead to comparative reduction emissions. A scenario highlighting a 1% increase in emission-reduction of highest 30% income-earners is visualized asT_S1.

Comprehensive scenario: Last, we also evaluated a comprehensive scenario, indicating the BAU contributions of specific commodities and respective reductions from transformations E_S1, E_S2, and T_S1. This comprehensive scenario was attempted to foresee if India can reach net-zero emissions by 2050.

Total carbon-budget of India: The value of India's carbon-budget of 2227 MtCO₂ per annum, is calculated by assuming India's share of 17.5% within the world's population, and annual global carbon budget (assumed till 2050) of equal to 12.73 (= 420/33, 33 years since reported till 2017) Gigatonnes (Gt) CO₂ per annum. The total carbon-budget of the world till 2050 is 420 Gt under the 1.5°C scenario emissions [42]).

Population estimates within land-based carbon-budget: The estimate of the population having a current average per capita within the food-based land-oriented share of India (2.2% of world's land area) of nearly 103.4 MtCO₂ per annum is also evaluated.

Table T.4: RE-transformation, capacity and emissions

Year	Capacity-(GW, C)	Capacity-Actual(GW) (Y)	Capacity-estimated(GW) (Y)(growth rate (0.23-higher))	Capacity-estimated (Y)(growth rate (0.172-Current))	Total Generation emissions-without RE	Emission per unit-higher capacity	Total emissions MT-higher	Emission per unit-lower capacity	Total emissions MT-current
2011	2184	14	14	14	548	0.92	504	0.92	504
2012	2184	0	18	17	582	0.92	534	0.92	535
2013	2184	0	22	20	622	0.92	570	0.92	571
2014	2184	0	28	23	662	0.91	605	0.92	607
2015	2184	0	35	28	719	0.91	655	0.91	658
2016	2184	33	44	33	786	0.91	713	0.91	717
2017	2184	40	55	39	852	0.90	769	0.91	775
2018	2184	0	69	46	913	0.90	819	0.91	828
2019	2184	0	86	54	982	0.89	873	0.90	887
2020	2184	0	107	64	992	0.88	873	0.90	892
2021	2184	0	133	76	1002	0.87	871	0.89	896
2022	2184	0	165	89	1065	0.86	911	0.89	945
2023	2184	0	204	105	1131	0.84	950	0.88	997
2024	2184	0	250	124	1201	0.82	985	0.87	1049
2025	2184	0	306	145	1276	0.80	1016	0.86	1103
2026	2184	0	372	170	1355	0.77	1041	0.85	1157
2027	2184	0	448	199	1438	0.74	1058	0.84	1210
2028	2184	0	536	232	1526	0.70	1067	0.83	1263
2029	2184	0	634	270	1619	0.66	1064	0.81	1314
2030	2184	0	742	314	1718	0.61	1050	0.79	1362
2031	2184	0	859	362	1799	0.56	1011	0.77	1389
2032	2184	0	981	417	1883	0.51	960	0.75	1410
2033	2184	0	1106	478	1970	0.46	900	0.72	1425
2034	2184	0	1231	545	2061	0.40	833	0.70	1433
2035	2184	0	1352	617	2155	0.35	760	0.66	1432
2036	2184	0	1467	696	2253	0.30	685	0.63	1422
2037	2184	0	1573	779	2355	0.26	610	0.60	1403
2038	2184	0	1669	867	2461	0.22	537	0.56	1374
2039	2184	0	1754	958	2570	0.18	469	0.52	1336
2040	2184	0	1828	1050	2684	0.15	405	0.48	1290
2041	2184	0	1891	1144	2767	0.12	343	0.44	1220
2042	2184	0	1945	1236	2852	0.10	289	0.40	1146
2043	2184	0	1989	1327	2939	0.08	242	0.36	1068
2044	2184	0	2026	1414	3029	0.07	202	0.33	989
2045	2184	0	2057	1497	3120	0.05	168	0.29	909
2046	2184	0	2082	1575	3214	0.04	139	0.26	830
2047	2184	0	2102	1647	3311	0.03	115	0.23	754
2048	2184	0	2118	1713	3410	0.03	95	0.20	681
2049	2184	0	2131	1773	3512	0.02	78	0.17	611
2050	2184	0	2142	1827	3616	0.02	64	0.15	547

S.3 Additional results

Since the main paper presented results at inter-state level (with data indicated in Appendix-04, Tabs ‘Fig3a’, ‘Fig3b’, and ‘Fig3c’), herein the visualizations specifically focus on intra-state, expenditure-wise distribution of impacts observed across regions (urban and rural).

S.3.1 Per capita emissions

The following is a brief summary of expenditure-wise impacts of some states, while detailed calculations of per capita emissions of all the states are given data file Appendix-02 (excel-sheet).

S.3.1.1 State-wise

Figure F.1: Per capita emissions: State-wise

Since the UT of Lakshadweep was excluded in the main paper owing to very high capita emissions, herein, we start with the results of the same. For Lakshadweep, the highest category (95 to 100%) in urban-areas had an average emission of 34.59 tCO₂eq (see Figure F.1, states arranged in decreasing average per capita) whereas the lowest category (0 to 5%) created an impact of about 2.42 tCO₂eq. The highest category of rural areas of Lakshadweep had average emissions of 30.24 tCO₂eq (95 to 100%) whereas the lowest category (0 to 5%) caused an impact of about 2.27 tCO₂eq. At the lower end of the national spectrum, the highest EC of urban-Bihar had an impact of 3.39 tCO₂eq, whereas the lowest EC in rural-Bihar were living with only 0.63 tCO₂eq. Considering other states and UTs in Figure F.1, we observe UTs (Lakshadweep, Puducherry, Daman, Dadra, Andaman, Chandigarh) tend to display higher per capita emissions. The lowest EC (< 5%) of urban-Goa had an average per capita of 2.18 tCO₂eq, whereas the highest 5% created an impact of around 12.70 tCO₂eq. For specific details of other states and UTs, see Tabs ‘PA_U_PCinT’ and ‘PA_R_PCinT’ of data file Appendix-02 (excel-sheet).

Further, results visualized in Figure 3a of the main paper are indicated in Appendix-04 (excel file), Tab ‘Fig 3a’. The said numbers were obtained when top and bottom 10% groups were combined to provide average estimates. The brief summary of said results is as follows. For urban-India, highest per capita average is recorded for Goa at 5.58 tCO₂ eq and lowest for Bihar at 1.54 tCO₂eq. For rural-India, highest per capita average is recorded for Goa at 5.54 tCO₂ eq and lowest for Bihar at 1.3 tCO₂eq. The state with the highest reported gross state domestic product [30] for the year 2011-12, namely Maharashtra, the average rural and urban emissions of nearly 2.07 and 2.56 tonnes CO₂ eq per capita, respectively, were recorded. Furthermore,

all heavily populated states including Bihar, Uttar Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh, Chattisgarh, Maharashtra, etc.; along with economically backward states (marked by State Gross Domestic Product (SGDP) [30]) of Manipur and Meghalaya are the ones with least values of per capita consumption emissions. The numbers of rural and urban population for the year 2011-2012 of each state are also reported in Appendix-02 (excel-file), Tab “Inequal_PC”.

S.3.1.2 Commodity-wise emissions of quantiles

Commodity-wise emissions for different quantiles are presented in Figures F.2(a) and F.2(b) for urban and rural categories, respectively. These figures clearly suggest that the topmost expenditure-category causes the largest per capita emissions.

Figure F.2: (a) Expenditure-wise per capita: Urban, commodities and (b) Expenditure-wise per capita emissions: Rural, Commodities

From the perspective commodity-wise emissions, Figure F.2(a) indicates that for the lowermost EC, urban emissions are 0.58 tCO₂eq for fuel and electricity, 0.07 tCO₂eq for transportation, 0.26 tCO₂eq for meat, 0.19 tCO₂eq for dairy products. 0.13 tCO₂eq for rice, 0.03 for footwear, 0.01 for edible oil, and 0.03 for others, whereas for the topmost EC, the average estimates are 2.15 tCO₂eq for fuel and electricity, 2.28 tCO₂ eq for transportation, 1.41 tCO₂eq for dairy products, 1.15 tCO₂e for meat, 0.13 tCO₂eq for rice, 0.21 for footwear, 0.03 for edible oil, and 0.15 for other commodities. For other categories, see rows 1453-1488 in Tab ‘PA_U_PCinT’ of Appendix-02.

Similarly, referring to the results of Figure F.2(b), the key per capita results for lowest EC in rural-category are 0.72 tCO₂eq for fuel and electricity, 0.08 tCO₂eq for transportation, 0.21 tCO₂eq for meat, 0.16 tCO₂eq for dairy products and 0.14 tCO₂eq for rice, whereas for highest expenditure-category in rural areas the average estimates are 2.02 tCO₂eq for fuel and electricity, 2.23 tCO₂eq for transportation, 1.14 tCO₂eq for meat, 1.11 tCO₂eq for dairy products and 0.16 tCO₂eq for rice. For other categories, see rows 1381-1416 in Tab ‘PA_R_PCinT’ of Appendix-02.

S.3.1.3 Rural versus Urban differences: State-level

Figure F.3 bifurcates the results across the rural and urban boundary for all states with specific averages, estimated as an average of the averages observed across states. Referring to the results of urban-India, Figure F.3 (a), it was discovered that nearly 23 states have consumption emissions lesser than the average estimate for the nation (3.16) in the urban category. The highest per capita emissions are displayed by nearly all UTs except Chandigarh, a few northern states, including the national capital city of Delhi in the rural category. Additionally, only the states of Goa, Kerala, and Tamil Nadu in southern India exceed the value of national average per capita emissions. To indicate the level of inequality within states, the lowest EC in Bihar had total emissions of 0.63 tCO₂eq compared to 3.39 tCO₂eq for highest EC; whereas the lowest EC in Lakswadeep had total emissions of 2.43 tCO₂eq compared to 34.59t CO₂eq for highest EC. The highest EC

S.3.2.1 State-wise TE

Following we state the numbers for the ten largest contributors (with urban-share of emissions and urban-population in % terms). The states with largest population, namely, Uttar Pradesh (≈ 307 MtCO₂eq, 27%, 21%), Maharashtra (≈ 242 MtCO₂eq, 54%, 49%), Andhra Pradesh (≈ 225 MtCO₂eq, 33% and 33%), Tamil Nadu (≈ 208 MtCO₂eq, 49%, population 61%), West Bengal (≈ 209 MtCO₂eq, 31%, 27%), Rajasthan (≈ 173 MtCO₂eq, 23%, 24%), Gujarat (≈ 150 MtCO₂eq, 43%, 40%), Karnataka (≈ 142 MtCO₂eq, 37%, 36%), Bihar (≈ 124 MtCO₂eq, 10%, 11%), and Kerala (≈ 115 MtCO₂eq, 27%, 26%), respectively. The details of other states can be found in SI-02 (excel-sheet), Tab “Summary_CF_UR_MT”. These results highlight that both larger population, sepcifically referring to rural-conglomerations, and highest per capita emissions (referring to north-east and northern India along with UTs) play a decisive role in generating emissions.

Figure F.4: State-wise TE: All States

S.3.2.2 Commodity-wise TE

Since national-level emissions were reported in Figure 3(b) of the main manuscript; herein, the state-wise contribution is summarized for the largest four commodities while the results are visualized in Figure F.5. The complete numbers of emissions of all four commodities are reported in Appendix-02 (excel-file), in Tabs ‘Summary_MC_URTot’, ‘Summary_MC_U_TF’ and ‘Summary_MC_R_TF’.

Analyzing results for rural areas (Tab ‘Summary_MC_R_TF’), Figure F.5(a) indicates that the state of Uttar Pradesh had the highest share of fuel emissions in the rural category at 76 MtCO₂eq. Further, at the state level (Tab ‘Summary_MC_URTot’), Uttar Pradesh is also the one with the largest share of total emissions of about 108 MtCO₂eq (nearly 10.6% of national) in the fuels category. In urban-context, Maharashtra had the largest contribution with 46.25 MtCO₂eq (or, nearly 14.7% of national-urban emissions) followed by Tamil Nadu with 38.39 MtCO₂eq (12.2% of national-urban emissions) and Uttar Pradesh with 31.54 MtCO₂eq (or, nearly 10.04% of national-urban emissions).

In the category of dairy products, Figure F.5(b) indicates that most substantial value of emissions is for Uttar Pradesh at 109.5 MtCO₂eq, with the urban share being approximately 25%. The state of Rajasthan follows Uttar Pradesh in milk products consumption with total emissions of nearly 70.6 MtCO₂eq and rural share being 75%. Maharashtra follows next with nearly 48.5 MtCO₂eq ($\approx 8\%$ of national milk emissions), and rural share of 43%.

Figure F.5(c) indicates the emissions of ‘egg, meat, and fish’ category, wherein the largest emissions are seen for the state of West Bengal at 83.7 MtCO₂eq with the rural share of 55.1 MtCO₂eq. This is followed by Andhra Pradesh with total emissions of 56.5 MtCO₂eq with the rural share of 36.35 MtCO₂eq (or, 64.3%).

Figure F.5: Total emissions (a) Fuels, (b) Milk, (c) Meat, fish and eggs, and (d) transportation

Tamil Nadu and Kerala follow successively with a share of approximately 11% and 8.8%, respectively at the national level.

The last Figure F.5(d) indicates the emissions associated with transportation. In this commodity, the largest emissions were seen for Gujarat and Maharashtra with intensities equivalent to 36.3 and 34 MTCO₂eq, respectively. Further, the share of urban emissions for these states is 40.6% and 42.3%, respectively. For additional results of the urban and rural share of other states, refer to Appendix-02, tab ‘MC_U_TF’ and ‘MC_R_TF’.

These results highlight the differences between specific consumption choices, especially for food-category and transportation. Such results are expected to be useful for policy planning related to the transportation sector and food or rather, nutritional security of India.

S.3.2.3 Expenditure-wise TE

Figure F.6 presents the expenditure-wise contributions of states across rural and urban dimensions, with detailed results indicated in Appendix-02, Tabs ‘Urban-CF-MillionTonne’ and ‘Rural-CF-MillionTonne’. Arranged in descending order of magnitude only 15 largest contributing states are indicated in Figure F.6 in both urban and rural context. Thus, these results highlight where most economically better-off people are settled in; and what is the total impact of their consumption.

Figure F.6: Expenditure-wise largest TE contributed by states: (a) Urban (b) Rural

Figure F.6(a) highlights the contribution of Maharashtra being the largest in the urban category, which is hardly surprising because it is home to the financial capital of India, the city of Mumbai. The other prominent contributors are indicated as well. Referring to the status of rural India, Figure F.6(b) shows the state of Uttar Pradesh has the largest emissions. Since the TE numbers represent the integration of the total population and per capita emissions, Figure F.6 present the total picture at the state-level.

S.3.3 Inequality analysis

S.3.3.1 State-wise

Data for Figure F.7 is indicated in Appendix-02, Tabs ‘Urban-CF-MillionTonne’ (row 1339-1376) and ‘Rural-CF-MillionTonne’(row 1336-1373).

Section 3.3 of the main paper presented combined results at state-level, herein results are presented at urban and rural dimensions. With Figure 4(a) of the main paper indicating inequality in terms ‘10/10’ ratios, Figure F.7 and this section discusses results in terms of ‘5/5’.

Figure F.7: State-wise inequity ratios (in terms of total emissions)

Assessing the level of inequality of urban-India (see Column T titled ‘ratio (high /low)’ in Appendix-02, Tab ‘Inequal_PC’), it was observed that highest ratios are for Lakswadeep (14.26), Chattisgarh (8.44), Uttar Pradesh (8.19), Haryana (8.16), Chandigarh (7.97), Delhi (7.62), West Bengal (7.56), Maharashtra (7.22), Madhya Pradesh (6.74), Jharkhand (6.44), Arunanchal Pradesh (6.15), Uttarakhand (5.98), Punjab (5.96), Gujarat (5.87), and Goa (5.82). In essence, all have values above the average of the country (5.77). Further, the lowest expenditure-category in Uttar Pradesh emitted 0.76 tCO₂eq per capita, whereas the highest emitted 6.24 tCO₂eq per capita. Similarly, numbers for Haryana were 1.33 to 10.83 (low to high), for Maharashtra 0.97 to 6.98, among others.

Referring to results of rural-India in Tab ‘Inequal_PC’ in Appendix-02, the lowermost EC of Madhya Pradesh emits the least at 0.59 tCO₂eq per capita followed by Uttar Pradesh and Bihar at 0.63 tCO₂eq per capita, whereas, the highest expenditure group of the coastal territory of the Lakshwadeep islands emitted nearly 30.340 tCO₂eq per person. The state of Manipur had the least difference between emissions of the lowest and the highest ECs (equal to 1.889 tCO₂eq), whereas the UT of Lakshwadeep had highest (28.073 tCO₂eq). Further, Goa, a UT, had a difference of 10.575 tCO₂eq; whereas, at the state level, for Haryana, a difference of 7.268 tCO₂eq was observed in the rural category.

Further, analysing the results of rural-India in Tab ‘Inequal_PC’ in Appendix-02, for the most populated states (Tabs ‘Summary - CF_UR_MT’ and ‘Pop_R_MRP’) of Uttar Pradesh (nearly 18.2% of national rural population), Bihar (10.7%), West Bengal (7.9%), Maharashtra (7.2%), Andhra Pradesh (6.8%), Madhya Pradesh (6.2%), and Rajasthan (5.9%), largest inequality of emissions between expenditure groups (lowest versus highest expenditure category) was observed for the state of Rajasthan (4.665 tCO₂eq), and least for Bihar (1.936 tCO₂eq). Excluding UTs and Goa (12.62 tCO₂eq). The emissions of topmost EC within rural India were highest for the state of Haryana at 8.37 tCO₂eq, followed by Arunanchal Pradesh at 7.78 tCO₂eq. These numbers are also indicated in the results of Figure 2(a) of the main paper. The average per capita of

UT of Lakshwadeep is 9.518, the highest in the country, whereas the lowermost EC of the UT of ‘Daman & Diu’ emitted largest with 3.003 tCO₂eq.

These results suggest that the poor (lowest EC) in the rural area of ‘Daman & Diu’ were best placed and of ‘Madhya Pradesh’ were in worst conditions in the nation. Further, only 9 states (including 4 UTs and national capital), namely, Lakshwadeep, Goa, Puducherry, Haryana, A & N Islands, Dadra & N. Haveli, Delhi, Kerala and Punjab have differences between highest to lowest ECs greater than the national average of 5.83 tCO₂eq. For additional results, refer to Appendix-02 (excel-sheet), Tab ‘Inequal_PC’.

Additionally, combining rural and urban emissions within same quintiles (not visualized here, numbers given in specific data sheets mentioned above), the “combined” results indicate that while topmost EC of Lakshwadeep emits 32.47 tCO₂eq, the lowest EC emits 2.36 tCO₂eq only. In comparison, the topmost EC of Bihar (the state with the one of the lowest TE and one of the largest population) emits 2.98 and lowest 0.63 tCO₂eqs only.

S.3.3.2 Commodity-wise

Data for Figures F.8 is indicated in Appendix-02, Tabs ‘Urban-CF-MillionTonne’ (row 1298-1332) and ‘Rural-CF-MillionTonne’ (row 1298-1332). To highlight the level of inequality between expenditure-group for commodities, the ratio of emissions by highest to lowest expenditure-category for different commodities were estimated, using Equation 7.

Figure F.8: Commodities-wise inequality ratios

$$R_{s,p,c}^* = \frac{CeI_{s,p,c,i=12}^h}{CeI_{s,p,c,i=1}^l} \quad (7)$$

Wherein $R_{s,p}^*$ indicates the ratio for profile p (rural or urban) of the state s , and $CeI_{s,p,c,i=12}^h$ and $CeI_{s,p,c,i=1}^l$ indicates per capita emissions for a specific commodity for highest (h) and lowest (l) ECs, respectively. The complete results of other commodities can be estimated using per capita and total emissions data of rural and urban categories indicated in Appendix-02. Furthermore, these ratios can be calculated for other ECs as well.

The summary of inequality ratios, in terms of per capita, of the four main commodities (fuel, milk, egg & meat, and transportation) is as follows, whereas the data is summarized in Appendix-02, Tab ‘Inequal.Comm’. For urban-India, the ratio of ‘fuel and electricity use’ stands at 3.28, whereas for transportation it is estimated as 35.0, 7.27 for milk and 4.36 for meat. For rural-India, ‘fuel and electricity use’ ratio is 2.82, transportation is 26.32, milk is 6.99, and for meat, the ratio is 5.41. These numbers indicate that except for meat-products, urban-India is far more inequitable than rural India. Figure 4(b) in the main paper indicate animal-based products are less inequitable in urban-India, whereas, these numbers indicate

milk-based inequality between the lowest and the highest is higher in urban-India. This causes serious issues to milk-security of northern-states since southern India is more attuned to meat-based diets [6].

For measuring inequality of specific commodities in terms of total emissions, Equation 8 is used,

$$R_{s,p,c}^{**} = \frac{TE_{s,p,c,i=12}^h}{TE_{s,p,c,i=1}^l} \quad (8)$$

wherein $R_{s,p}^{**}$ indicates the ratio for profile p (rural or urban) of the state s , and $TE_{s,p,c,i=12}^h$ and $TE_{s,p,c,i=1}^l$ indicates total emissions for a specific commodity for highest (h) and lowest (l) ECs, respectively. The results of this estimation for the main commodities are also indicated in Appendix-02, Tab ‘Inequal_Comm’, whereas summary as follows.

The summary of inequality ratios, in terms of total emissions, of the main commodities is as follows. For urban-India, the ratio of ‘fuel and electricity use’ stands at 4.71, whereas for transportation it is estimated as 42.48, 8.06 for milk, 4.9 for meat. For rural-India, ‘fuel and electricity use’ ratio is 2.76, transportation is 20.83, milk is 10.11, and for meat, the ratio is 6.21. These numbers indicate that except for food-commodities, urban-India is far more inequitable than rural India, as is also gathered from Figure 4(b) in the main paper. These ratios can be estimated for other ECs, other commodities and at the state level as well using the data given in Appendix-02, Tabs ‘PA_R_PCinT’, ‘PA_U_PCPerinT’, ‘RCF_MT’, and ‘UCF_MT’.

The above-stated ratios and information conveyed through Figures F.2(a) and (b), suggest consumption of dairy products is more inequitable than that of meat, while transportation impacts are more inequitable than ‘fuel and electricity use’.

S.3.3.3 Lorentz curves and Gini Coefficient

Estimating inequality this study plotted, Lorentz curves along with evaluating Gini coefficients, for rural and urban dimension, separately. Figure F.9 offers visualization in a spatial context. The Gini coefficient is calculated as the ratio of the area between the equality line at 45° and inequality curve and area beneath the equality line at 45°. The calculations of same are indicated in Appendix-02, under the tabs ‘Lorentz curve, Gini- Urban’ and ‘Lorentz curve, Gini- Rural’.

Figure F.9: Lorentz curves at national level: (a) Urban (b) Rural

S.3.4 Comparison with other studies

Consumption-oriented carbon-footprints are largely unavailable for rural and urban India at state-level [13, 43, 6, 9], with sector-wise and urban assessments capturing techno-economic perspective being more widespread [13, 44, 37, 45, 46, 43]. Further, significant differences exist in the scope of assessments due to using different methods and for different time-periods. For example, life-cycle aspect was captured at economic-scale [13] for 2003-04, consumption-oriented product/process-based assessments are largely lacking

especially at comprehensive, national and regional scales. Further, consumer-survey based consumption-oriented assessments for recent years mostly focused on food-energy-water demands [1, 47]. Thus, neglecting the role of appliances, buildings, vehicles, infrastructure, and supply-chains at the regional scale. Hence, the comparison attempted next is limited in scope to sector-wise and spatial scale.

The TE of 2605 MtCO₂eq is higher than the value reported by The World Bank for 2014, equal to 2238 MtCO₂eq [48] and those reported by WIOD environmental accounts (nearly 2183 MtCO₂eq in 2008) [11]. Using energy emission-intensities reported in [9], electricity-based emissions of nearly 507 MtCO₂eq (assuming 50% fuel-based expenditure -pg 9 of NSS [4]) are reported. This number is lower in comparison to those reported by global emissions database, i.e. 760 MtCO₂eq (58% [29] of total power sector emissions [49], used by [43]) and higher than CEA number of 370 MtCO₂eq ($0.58 * 637.8$ [50]). The transportation emissions of 275 MtCO₂eq are higher than those reported by [49] and those reported for road transport for 2011 (170 MtCO₂eq, including road emissions due to motor spirit, furnace oil, high-speed diesel oil, light diesel oil, and LPG used in the retail sector) under GWP-AR2 method [51].

Comparing food estimates from another study [6] our study corroborates that emission-impact of wheat consumption are less compared to rice, milk, and meat. The per capita value of 2.35 tCO₂eq is higher than [13] (reported for 2003-04), while studies at urban-scale [47, 1] offer limited comparison. As most referred studies are performed at different scales/system boundaries and at different time-periods, thus fair and comprehensive comparisons are not possible with the current study. Considering that underlying assumptions, especially about emission-intensities [45] in CO₂ databases ([49]- EDGAR and CEA [50]) and scope of assessments also differ, such variation is expected.

Thus, we see, India's emissions databases ignore some emissions-categories, especially those related to food (milk and meat). This study indicates that nearly 1039 MtCO₂eq ([52]- Milk will drive methane emissions in India) are created by these categories. Further, transport and fuel emissions accounted for nearly 1290 MtCO₂eq. Since industries use almost 42% of fossil-based energy, this implies industrial emissions amount to nearly 934 MtCO₂eq. This makes India's fossil fuel emissions around 2224 MtCO₂eq for 2011-12. Adding agricultural and meat milk emissions, make India's GHG emissions around 3540 MtCO₂eq as per our study, while EDGAR database [53] indicates GHG emissions of 3240 MtCO₂eq, another EDGAR report indicates 3020 MtCO₂eq (2011-[54]). It is to be noted that EDGAR database neglects certain categories, such as land-use and biomass-based emissions, (see limitations on pg 2- [55]). While our study accounts some of them due to consumption-expenditure and biomass-based intensities (though aggregated with LPG and other domestic fuels) used in our study. Thus, our direct GHG estimates of households consumption numbers account for nearly 74% (2605/3540) of India's total GHG emissions.

S.3.4.1 Comparison with IO-based carbon-studies

In the context of India, EEIO-based studies [13, 56, 57, 58] have reported rather 'irregular' emission-estimates of households' consumption. For example, a recent application of multi-regional EORA-model for India [58] indicated national average carbon-footprint of 0.56 tCO₂ per capita (using 2011-12 consumer survey data), which is difficult to justify in view of those reported earlier (1.8 tCO₂, [56], 1.6 tCO₂ [13], 0.8 tCO₂ [57]), and GHG emissions by other reports [53, 59, 60]. Such discrepancy may be due to substantial variation observed in regional consumer-prices reported in expenditure-survey data [4, 3], even though equal value of carbon-intensities (in monetary-terms) are derived from the EEIO-literature. For instance, consumption expenditures tend to be higher in urban areas due to higher disposable income [3], whereas, per unit commodities-prices, except for fuels, are lower in rural areas (Tables 4U/R-a/b in [4]).

As stated in the main manuscript, a substantial variation is observed in regional commodity-prices in the expenditure survey of India (Tables 4U/R-a/b in [4]). Such variation in commodity-prices implies the same emission-intensity(price-based) derived from EEIO models would undermine consumption for regions with lower per commodity prices and overstate it for regions with higher per commodity prices. Further, when commodities such as biofuels (firewood, chips, etc. harvested from local forest-reserves [61, 62]) do not enter the market-system, EEIO-models cannot map impacts of such consumption. That is, EEIOs such EORA or EXIOBASE cannot estimate impacts of consumption that are not recorded in the national IO tables.

As stated earlier current study follows a bottom-up approach and uses emissions divided in scope 1,2, and 3 categories for specific products and not sectors it differs from Pachauri's book and Parikh's study in 2009. Further, in IO-based studies, if final demand vector is aggregated, it cannot differentiate between

household-consumers, government spending, imports/exports, among others. Whereas, the current study using exclusively household expenditure avoids such a trap.

Parikh's study (2009), using the 2003-04 SAM of India, focused on the economic structure of India. It estimated CO₂ emissions of (aggregated) 25 sectors (2003-04 SAM consisted of 73 production sectors and 10 expenditure classes) while retaining the major energy-producing and using sectors, and, 10 expenditure-classes (5 rural and 5 urban). Thus, the major focus of this study was the energy sectors. The study states verbatim "*The emission coefficients by fuel type used in this study are 1.614 and 3.102 tons of CO₂ per ton of coal and petroleum products, respectively, and 0.0021 tons of CO₂ per cubic metre of natural gas.*" .

Focusing on economic sectors results indicated direct CO₂ emissions of 1128 MT and total CO₂ emissions of 1217 MT and per capita of 1.14 (using total emissions), with a population of 1072 million. From a production perspective, electricity accounted for 57% of emissions, followed by manufacturing, steel and road transportation. Whereas, from a consumption perspective, total household emissions (primarily consisting of domestic fuel, electricity and transport) amounted to 707 MT. Thus, HH emissions accounted for 58% of total emissions. Further, it indicated that the urban top 10% accounts for emissions of 3416 kg per year while rural bottom 10% class accounts for only 141 kg per year. The results of this study beat the projections made by another study by the same researchers (Parikh et al., 1997. Consumption patterns by expenditure-groups and carbon-dioxide implications for India: 1990-2010.), which indicated 502 MtCO₂ by 2010. Household per capita average is 0.66 tCO₂. Average urban capita from Parikh is 1.16 tCO₂, rural per capita 0.465 tCO₂. Using per capita, urban disparity (15:1) higher than rural (9:1).

Differences in scope with the current study from Parikh, 2009:

- Time period 2003-04
- Population level of 1072 in 2003-04, current study 1108 million
- Aggregation of expenditure levels
- No mention of food-based emissions, milk, meat, in particular.
- No information on state-level -per capita, Total, inequality.

Similar results:

- Urban disparity higher than rural
- Transport emissions-highest inequality amongst top and bottom 10

The sector-wise estimates from IO-based study of 2003-04 are not readily usable for consumer-survey accounts for 2011-12, since consumer expenditure covers a significant portion of food, and apparel categories, which are missing in Parikh's study. Further, neither state-level comparison is possible, nor anything can be said about any state's total population. Additionally, it is not possible to compare the expenditure of categories without considering inflation-deflation indices between years too. Furthermore, though IO-based production analysis from Parikh points to the indirect role of construction, agro-processing, its contribution in consumption-side is missing as well. The link of the construction sector with expenditure for education, medical-expenses, capital-goods, etc., is not accounted for even in Parikh's study.

Our study has a little over 8 years difference with Parikh study, and a population difference of 36 million. Further, we are using consumer survey as the assessment boundary, incorporating state-level expenditure data. Thus, the boundary of our assessment completely differs from Parikh in time, population-level, perspective, and methodology. Further, peculiarities are as follows.

In our study, owing to the lack of emissions associated with education, medical-expenses, capital-goods, etc., and lack of expenditure-data within categories, such exclusions were made. Further, certain goods such as cars and houses are purchased in one year but are taken on credit-system that runs in years to decades. Thus, consumer expenditure does not align well with construction, capital goods, or the industrial sector, in consumer survey accounts.

However, from consumer-perspective, food was given due consideration from the perspective of nutrition-oriented carbon-intensive diets. Thus, we accounted for GHG emissions (given by FAO) in our estimates that Parikh's study neglected. After including food-based emissions, our study indicates a lower level of urban versus rural disparity, though transport shows a similar trajectory. That is, private transport is the

most unequal contributor of emissions within the top to bottom 10% in India. Considering the household's transport emissions Parikh's study reported 68MT or 5.8% (68/1210) contribution, while our study indicates the contribution of transportation around 275MT or 7.8% (275/3540 MT) and domestic fuel. It is to be noted EDGAR database reports around 3.2 GtCO₂eq for 2012, while another study ([63]) reported 3202 MtCO₂eq and per capita of 2.48 tCO₂ eq for 2014. The higher transportation numbers can be justified owing growing use of 4-wheelers for private commute over the differences in period.

Referring to Pauchari book (An Energy Analysis of Household Consumption Changing Patterns of Direct and Indirect Use In India), the IO tables used are from 1989-99 to 1998-99, with a necessary aggregation of sector's composition and price corrections for different years. In the field of Industrial Ecology, aggregation is a big issue (see- M. Lenzen. Aggregation versus disaggregation in the input-output analysis of the environment, 2011. Economic Systems Research 23(1):73-89. And, M. Lenzen. Aggregating input-output systems with minimum error. 2019. Economic Systems Research. 31(4):594-616.) Further Pauchari's study had a minimum gap of 12 years gap from our study and used IO-based Household expenditure data to map growth in emissions over the years. Thus, the scope and boundary of analysis again differed from our study. Pachauri's recent work ([43]) on the electricity sector's emissions for 2011-12 excludes emissions of food, transport, and fuel, among others, and neither it focuses on expenditure-categories or states.

Since the referenced studies differ in scope and time-frame from the current study. Hence, the comparison of our research with these referenced studies does not yield much insight concerning our boundary of analysis. Further, except for highlighting two sectors of electricity production and transport systems, owing to their direct use of energy-based resources, an absolute comparison is not possible.

S.3.4.2 Comparison with urban metabolism-based studies

Comparison with Boyer and Ramaswami [47, 1] Boyer and Ramaswami [47, 1] have published work in the context of urban-metabolism in India. But, their dataset is limited to certain cities with a highly variable set of population. Most cities considered were Union Territories of India (thus, their separate administrative boundary allowed assessments). Food-total includes the industrial total for some cities and is excluded for others. Neither the all-India picture is presented in their work. Their work also does not involve building emissions inventories for any regions and use data from sources included in this work, FAO, CO₂-emissions reported by Pathak et al., etc., among others. Further, they do not focus on inequality. Thus, the scope of their study is much different than our assessment. Comparison with Boyer [1] is presented in Table T.5. The numbers from Boyer's study are estimated from figures since data is not available. Neither is per commodity emissions are available, for detailed verification.

Table T.5: Comparison with Boyer et al.[1]

City	State	Population, Millions		Per capita emissions food-based, tCO ₂ eq			Total emissions, MtCO ₂ eq				
		Boyer	Our study	First order	Boyer	Our estimation	Our study	Home	Industrial	Commercial	Total
Chandigarh	Chandigarh	1	0.91	0.24	0.67	1.60	0.07	0.5	0.1	0.67	1.46
Delhi	Delhi	16.4	11.69	0.33	1.18	1.50	4.3	11.9	3.1	19.3	17.53
Ahamdabad	Gujarat	5.6	22.57	0.21	0.00	0.30	*	*	*	0	6.69
Rajkot	Gujarat	1.3	22.57	0.2	0.00	0.07	*	*	*	0	1.55
Surat	Gujarat	4.5	22.57	0.21	0.00	0.24	*	*	*	0	5.38
Goa	Goa	1.5	0.65	0.39	1.27	2.16	1.2	0.6	0.1	1.9	1.406
Bangalore	Karnataka	8.4	29.52	0.33	0.00	0.25	*	*	*	0	7.50
Chennai	Tamil Nadu	4.6	30.15	0.37	0.00	0.25	*	*	*	0	7.56
Pondicherry	Pondicherry	1.2	0.76	0.52	1.92	2.18	1.2	0.7	0.4	2.3	1.66

^a- Data not available. Other data from Boyer extracted from figures.

^a*

Comparison with Moran, D. et al.[2] Moran, D. et al.[2] (compared in Table T.6) focuses on cities using a top-down approach involving global MRIO model that has many levels of aggregations. Further, using a clustering algorithm, it defines cities with density_c= 1500/km² and population_c= 50000 while using population-settlement mapping model, GHS-SMOD. As their method identifies clusters based on the contiguous urban fabric, they state that the boundary of clusters often includes suburbs and exurbs; thereby leading to larger urban areas compared to those defined under strict legal boundaries of a city’s jurisdictions. Thus, their clustering techniques overwhelmingly dictates both their population numbers and per capita emissions as discussed below. Further differences between limitations and assumptions of Moran’s study and our work are stated as follows:

- Equal distribution of infrastructural (education, health, water and sewage facilities) footprint to all expenditure-classes; we do not consider such emissions since sample survey does not offer clear information for all expenditure-categories for money spent on such services.
- Error in the national carbon-footprints results from Eora could be up to 25% for other countries (for developed nations the difference is up to 10%). We use a bottom-up approach excluding supply-chain emissions (which we consider under industrial emissions, and attribute them to business, not households). Our emission intensities refer to the specific boundary of scope 1,2 and 3 types of emissions (details indicated in methodology Section 2 of the main manuscript).
- Their study indicates that due to the use of IO tables, allocation and aggregation error are possible while matching purchasing patterns with the corresponding goods in the emission-IO models, Such errors could include accounting utilities in the rent, and varying carbon intensity of same sector goods (e.g. electricity may have different carbon intensity in different areas of a country).
- Their study provides per capita and total carbon footprint for 25 Indian cities, where some lie in the same state. And, since their population numbers and geographical boundaries differ from ours, it is difficult to compare and justify our numbers with them. That said, a comparison is attempted next to highlight why our numbers differ so much from them.

At the national level, the total population covered by them is 1250 million, Sample survey covers 1109 million. Comparison with specific cities is as follows- these are union territories with their own jurisdiction, and thus a comparison was possible.

Referring to Table T.6, comparing the population of Delhi only -in the National Sample Survey (used in our work) population number for Delhi is 12.7 million (rural plus urban). In Moran’s study, it is 27.2 million (urban). Per capita: 3.52tCO₂eq our study; 2. 6 tCO₂eq -Moran’s. Considering the numbers for Chandigarh in our study - the population is 0.98 million (rural plus urban) and per capita is 3.75 tCO₂eq In Moran’s study Chandigarh’s population is 2.2 million (urban) and per capita: 3.9 tCO₂eq our study. As per 2011 census, the population of Chandigarh was 10.6 million, the national sample survey excludes certain categories including floating population. Thus, we see a wide difference in population-level exist for total carbon-emissions in our and Moran’s work. Further comparison with other cities identified in Moran’s work is not possible since the consumer survey of India does not include any data on other Indian cities, (excluding the union territories of India).

All said, the key insight from their work is that emissions are driven by a combination of both population and affluence. We derive similar results for highly populous states and high expenditure-categories, in Sections 3.1 and 3.2.

Table T.6: Comparison with Moran et al.[2]

Urban Cluster	Country	Moran [2]			Footprint	1StdDev (calc. with cell-wise of coefficient of variation = 10.0)	Our Study						
		Footprint/Population	Population	Popln.			Urban Percap tCO ₂ eq	Total tCO ₂ eq	Popln.	Rural Percap tCO ₂ eq	Total tCO ₂ eq		
Ahmadabad	India	1.8	66,35,451	1,22,10,790	41,30,333								
Asansol	India	1.9	32,44,836	61,49,673	22,49,442								
Bangalore	India	2.0	1,05,92,040	2,16,30,460	54,73,214								
Bhopal	India	2.4	22,76,644	55,39,323	26,12,945								
Chandigarh	India	3.9	22,47,028	87,57,365	32,50,725			909400	3.28	29,80,559	70500	4.23	2,98,098
Chennai	India	2.3	94,83,131	2,18,41,040	52,68,994								
Cochin	India	1.8	25,07,854	45,19,027	11,04,802								
Coimbatore	India	3.2	22,13,202	71,73,353	30,58,239								
Hyderabad	India	3.2	83,96,463	2,65,47,500	83,97,809								
Jaipur	India	2.5	38,19,143	94,22,303	29,98,449								
Kanpur	India	1.7	37,76,208	65,37,981	26,22,730								
Kavaratti	India	1.5	33,93,635	51,29,819	16,51,789								
Kolkata	India	1.7	2,48,66,730	4,29,07,350	1,02,78,460								
Lucknow	India	1.8	45,90,620	84,79,963	38,37,371								
Ludhiana	India	2.9	20,81,258	59,90,197	27,74,023								
Mumbai	India	1.4	2,28,45,980	3,20,61,160	70,61,089								
Nagpur	India	2.8	29,82,625	83,28,866	32,83,715								
New Delhi	India	2.6	2,72,31,680	6,96,45,290	1,32,51,790			11692800	3.79	4,42,66,992	1004200	3.26	32,76,203
Pune	India	2.8	66,97,672	1,89,09,800	58,74,106								
Raipur	India	2.1	26,83,816	56,63,510	20,03,167								
Surat	India	1.0	46,36,731	45,55,489	20,74,553								
Unknown city at lat/lon 11.0, 75.9	India	2.0	48,32,714	95,21,231	20,37,768								
Unknown city at lat/lon 22.7, 75.8	India	2.6	28,44,387	75,13,536	35,28,255								
Vadodara	India	3.5	19,86,925	69,06,992	24,38,411								
Varanasi	India	1.1	41,65,070	45,83,309	20,45,350								

S.3.5 Results-Emissions scenarios: Households-based

Figure F.10: RE based capacity and emissions' reduction

Figure F.10 indicates 'Electricity; emissions along with reduction due to RE capacity detailed in Section S.2.3. The purpose of this figure is to illustrate the reduction in emissions due to differences in solar capacity. The numbers are given in Table T.4.

Referring to the food-based scenarios in the main paper, it was indicated through scenario F_S1 if India pursues nutritional trajectory, it can reduce food-based impact by 350 MtCO₂eq in 2050 compared to current trajectory. Or, cumulatively, under F_S1, it could reduce food-based emissions by 4296 MtCO₂eq or 4.3 GtCO₂eq from 2028 to 2050. On the other hand, if OECD-diets are pursued, meeting OECD-level of 2.899 tCO₂eq per capita in 2050, as visualized scenario F_S2, the total cumulative emissions from 2012 will increase (from F_BAU) nearly by 24592 MtCO₂eq or 24.6 GtCO₂eq by 2050. Or, reaching 4153 MtCo₂eq in 2050 from 1172 MtCO₂eq in 2011. It is to be noted that annual food-based carbon-budget of India (CB1) is only 822.5 MtCO₂eq [27]. Thus, even in 2011 India exceeded its fair share of food-budget owing to its larger population consuming less than nutritional-level. Using food-based carbon-budget as an ideal threshold level of population can also be evaluated for both nutritional and OECD-type of diets; however, such a number is not speculated in our assessment.

S.3.6 Note on total GHG and industrial GHG emissions:

Since industries consume 42% of energy, using fuel, electricity and transport emissions of consumption, total industrial emissions were estimated for the industry in 2011 were about 934 MtCO₂eq (1290/0.58). Thus, we estimate total GHG emissions of about 3539 MtCO₂eq in 2011. The EDGAR database (with all its uncertainties and limitations) reports total GHG emissions of India 3020 MtCO₂eq [54]. Using the same ratio of 42% for 2050, we estimate BAU-based total industrial emissions of 6165 MtCO₂eq in 2050, with conveyance share of 21% (or 1315 MtCO₂eq). The fuel and electricity are expected to contribute equally (2425 MtCO₂eq), with total leading to 4850 MtCO₂eq. However, with the installation of 100% solar capacity, the electricity emissions could reduce by 2619 MtCO₂eq. Thus, fuel and conveyance would emit about 3740 MTCo₂eq in 2050 without any changes in efficiency, and other transformations for fuel, conveyance, materials, etc. Thus, while total GHG emissions under BAU could reach 17.2 GtCO₂eq (or

17239 MtCO₂eq) in 2050, they could be reduced to 12GtCO₂eq (11795 MtCO₂eq) by the above-considered transformation in electricity and reduced travel emissions. The food emissions, if nutritional security is pursued beyond 2028, could be reduced by another 350 MtCO₂eq in 2050.

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